

What happened to the Spotify Model? - Artefacts

F. Gracia-Ahufinger
University of Seville
Seville, Spain

fragraahu@alum.us.es

Javier J. Gutiérrez
University of Seville
Seville, Spain

javierj@us.es

J.A. García-García
University of Seville
Seville, Spain

juliangg@us.es

Abstract

The present document introduces three of the artefacts used for the article What happened to the Spotify Model? On one hand a detailed table with the list of the primary studies analysed is introduced, including the title and bibliography reference. On the other hand a chapter that introduces the thematic mapping of the literature findings. And finally, a chapter that explain how this work was supported with the use of IA-driven data extraction, detailing the prompts used with this purpose.

A. List of Primary Studies and References

Table 1. List of Primary Studies

Primary Study Title	Ref.
A longitudinal explanatory case study of coordination in a very large development programme...	[9]
Achieving agility using business model stress testing	[4]
Adopting Collaborative Games into Agile Software Development	[56]
Agile Implementations in Cyber Security Issues Arising and Recommendations	[8]
Agile in the Era of Digitalization: A Finnish Survey Study	[20]
Agile tailoring in distributed large-scale environments using agile frameworks: A Systematic Literature Review	[5]
An architecture governance approach for Agile development by tailoring the Spotify model	[43]
Applying Model-Driven Engineering to Stimulate the Adoption of DevOps Processes...	[46]
Are Business Expectations Aligned with the Development Plan Made by the Software Architecture Area?...	[44]
Case Studies on ISD Agility	[7]
Challenges in scaling AI-powered distributed software product: A case study of a healthcare organization	[15]
Clarifying the Role of Product Owners: A Comprehensive Taxonomy on Product Owner Roles	[18]
Comparative Analysis of Software Process Models with an Agile Case Study: Lessons Learned...	[30]
Comparing Methods for Large-Scale Agile Software Development: A Systematic Literature Review	[11]
Consolidating Academic and Practical Guidelines for Digital Transformation	[53]
Coordination in Large-Scale Agile Software Development	[1]
Design and Development of a Standard Interface Component... in the Conta Azul Software	[24]
Design of transformation initiatives implementing organisational agility: an empirical study	[22]
Do Agile scaling approaches make a difference? an empirical comparison...	[54]
Evolution of the Agile Scaling Frameworks	[52]
Exploring the Microservice Development Process in Small and Medium-Sized Organizations	[45]
FAIR in action - a flexible framework to guide FAIRification	[55]
Finding the sweet spot for organizational control and team autonomy in large-scale agile...	[25]
Heterogeneous Tailoring Approach Using the Spotify Model	[41]
How Are Agile Release Trains Formed in Practice? A Case Study in a Large Financial Corporation	[33]
Industrial Agile Transformations Lacking Business Emphasis: Results from a Nordic Survey Study	[21]
Influential Factors of Aligning Spotify Squads in Mission-Critical and Offshore Projects...	[38]
Institutional Logics in Large-Scale Agile Software Development Transformations	[16]
Operationalizing Agile Methods: Examining Coherence in Large-Scale Agile Transformations	[6]
Orchestrating Agile IT Quality Management for Complex Solution Development...	[32]
Perspectives on the Sustainability and Future Trajectory of Agile	[13]
Predicting the Winners of Borda, Kemeny and Dodgson Elections with Supervised Machine Learning	[23]
Responding to change over time: A longitudinal case study on changes in coordination mechanisms...	[2]
Responding to Change: Agile-in-the-large, Approaches and Their Consequences	[17]
SAFe transformation in a large financial corporation	[34]
Scalable Agile Frameworks in Large Enterprise Project Portfolio Management	[48]
Scaling Agility in Large Software Development Projects: A Systematic Literature Review	[50]
Spotify Tailoring for Architectural Governance	[42]
Spotify Tailoring for B2B Product Development	[39]
Spotify Tailoring for Promoting Effectiveness in Cross-Functional Autonomous Squads	[40]
Stra2Bis: A Model-Driven Method for Aligning Business Strategy and Business Processes	[28]
Striving for a Freedom in a Large-Scale Agile Environment with an Entrepreneurial Mindset...	[26]
Tackling Alignment Challenges: A Light-Weight Method to Plan Business and IT Co-evolution	[27]
Team autonomy and digital transformation: Disruptions and adjustments in a well-established...	[35]
The EFIS Framework for Leveraging Agile Organizations Within Large Enterprises	[31]
The Impact of Agile Transformations on Organizational Performance: A Survey...	[47]
The State of Agile Software Development in the Czech Republic: Preliminary Findings...	[10]
Toward an Agile Product Management: What Do Product Managers Do in Agile Companies?	[49]
Towards Business Agility 2.0	[19]
Transition from Plan Driven to SAFe: Periodic Team Self-Assessment	[37]
Transition from Plan-Driven to Agile: An Action Research	[36]
Transitioning from a First Generation to Second Generation Large-Scale Agile Development Method...	[3]
Using Management Transaction Concept to Ensure Business and EAS Alignment in an Agile Environment	[29]
Using Social Network Analysis to Investigate the Collaboration Between Architects and Agile Teams...	[51]

B. Thematic Mapping of Literature Finding

This sections serves as the empirical foundation for the results discussed in the main paper. Table 2 maps specific organizational challenges, failures and limitations identified in the literature to their respective articles IDs. Table 3 maps the identified learnings and success factors. These findings demonstrate the evolution of the Spotify Model from its 2012 origin to its current state as a tailored industry practice.

Table 2. Challenges, Failures, or Limitations Identified in Literature

Challenges, Failures or Limitations	Article IDs
Coordination between Teams	[2], [5, 6], [9], [11], [13], [38, 39, 40, 41], [43], [48], [50]
Balancing Autonomy vs. Alignment & Control	[6], [11], [15], [25, 26], [35], [38], [40, 41, 42, 43]
Limitations “Not a model to copy” & Cargo Cult	[1], [11], [13], [17], [26], [40], [44], [52]
Challenges with Roles	[5, 6], [8], [11], [18], [26], [31], [39]
Limitations “Not for B2B” & Mission Critical	[5], [11], [38, 39, 40, 41], [43]
Lack of Architecture Governance	[5], [35], [41, 42, 43], [51]

Table 3. Learnings and Success Factors Identified in Literature

Learnings and Success Factors	Article IDs
Tailoring is Essential (Not Copying)	[2], [5], [11], [13], [16, 17], [26], [39, 40, 41, 42, 43, 44], [48], [52]
Guilds are Effective for Knowledge Sharing	[2], [7], [9], [11], [25], [31, 32], [38], [41], [43, 44, 45, 46], [49], [51]
Must Create Alignment Mechanisms	[6], [11], [15], [25], [31, 32], [38, 39, 40, 41, 42, 43], [48]
Focus on Culture over Structure	[6, 7], [11], [13], [15], [17], [31], [40], [43], [52]
Improve Employee Satisfaction & Motivation	[6], [11], [13], [16], [20], [25], [47], [52], [54]
Adding Governance (Architecture) is a Key Fix	[11], [35], [41, 42, 43], [45]

C. How IA has been used for this work

To optimize the synthesis of the 54 primary studies and ensure a structured analysis of the Spotify Model's evolution, this study employed *NotebookLM*, [14], a generative AI tool powered by the Gemini 1.5 Pro model. This Generative AI tool was employed for cross-study synthesis and the generation of the evolutionary infographic. To ensure the integrity of the research, a human-verified protocol was maintained, all AI-generated claims were traced back to source citations and the classifications were manually audited for accuracy. Following the ISD 2026 guidelines for AI disclosure, this artifact details the technical setup, prompts and validation protocols used.

Due to the platform's technical constraints of 50 sources per notebook, the review environment was split into two distinct notebooks to accommodate the 54 primary studies and required guidelines. Each of the notebooks contained 27 out of the 54 primary studies, 1 to 27 the first notebook and 28 to 54 the second notebook. Additionally, each of the notebooks also contained the guidelines to perform Rapid Reviews, [12].

The AI was utilized for thematic extraction and cross-study synthesis. Specific prompts were used to obtain answers to RQ.2 and RQ.3, as shown in the two first prompts in Table 4. Extraction prompts were iteratively tested on a control set of 20% of the studies and output were manually compared against a manual extraction to calibrate the prompts before processing the full dataset. Results from running both prompts in each notebook were merged by authors to consolidate the information and generate the table included in the article, which were then used to draw the Figures in the article.

Once the article was peer reviewed and ready for submission, a third notebook was created with a draft version of the article. Then, the third prompt was run in order to obtain the infographic for the evolution of the Spotify Model, shown in the article.

To mitigate the risk of AI hallucinations or inaccuracies, a rigorous human-verified protocol was followed. For every synthetic summary generated, the authors used NotebookLM citation feature to trace the claim back to the specific passage in the primary study. Additionally, 100% of the AI-generated classifications was manually audited by two of the authors to ensure the risk of bias and quality assessment remained accurate and consistent.

Table 4. Prompts used for thematic extraction

Prompt

Can you provide a table with the following data: First Column - Challenges, Failures or Limitations: Which Challenges, Failures or Limitations does the work discuss when adopting the Spotify Model in real world scenarios, considering the following ones: Balancing autonomy vs Alignment & Control, Coordination between Teams, Lack of Architecture Governance, Challenges with Roles, Limitations "Not a model to copy" & Cargo Cult, Limitations "Nor for B2B" & Mission Critical Second Column - Article IDs: ID of the selected work in the format PSxx Third Column - Count: Number of selected works that discuss the specific topic

Can you provide a table with the following data: First Column - Learnings and Success Factors: Which Learnings and Success Factors does the work discuss when adopting the Spotify Model in real world scenarios, considering the following ones: Tailoring is Essential (Not Copying), Must create alignment mechanisms, Focus on Culture over Structure, Adding governance (Architecture) is a Key Fix, Guilds are effective for knowledge sharing, Improve employees satisfaction & motivation Second Column - Article IDs: ID of the selected work in the format PSxx Third Column - Count: Number of selected works that discuss the specific topic

Create a horizontal timeline infographic modelled after Figures 3 and 8 from the Agile UX paper to show the evolution of the Spotify Model. Divide the content into three chronological phases: 1. Earlier Years (2012-2015) - Perception: Cultural Snapshot. Application: Introduction of Squads, Tribes, Chapters, and Guilds as an alternative to prescriptive frameworks like SAFe. 2. Middle Years (2016-2020) - Perception: Recognition of 'Cargo Cult' issues. Application: Struggle with 'Squad Goals' and role ambiguity. High interest in the 'Autonomy vs. Alignment' tension and coordination challenges. 3. Recent Years (2021-2025) - Perception: Tailored Practice. Application: Integration of Architectural Governance and formal alignment mechanisms. Essential focus on B2B and mission-critical contexts. Include a summary contrast section: - Past (Cargo Cult/Structural Focus): Copy-pasting structures without underlying culture, viewing the model as an 'aspirational' snapshot, and blind replication of Squads/Tribes. - Current/Future (Tailoring/Architectural Governance): Governance as a 'key fix', focus on engineering culture over structure, and adding formal alignment layers for B2B/regulated industries.

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